

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional ... (Dawodu, et. al., 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073605>

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy on Performance in Technical Education among Colleges of Education Students in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study examines the effect of the Mind Mapping Instructional strategy (MMIS) on Performance in Technical Education among Colleges of Education Students in South-West, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted Quasi-experimental design. The sample of the study consisted of 109 NCE II students, selected using purposive and random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was Technical Education Performance Test (TEPT) validated by three experts. The reliability coefficient of TEPT was 0.80 using the Kuder-Richardson formula 20. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, analysis of variance was used to test the hypothesis one and t-test to test hypothesis two. The results of the study showed that the mean performance scores of students taught using MMIS was significantly higher than that of students taught using Traditional Instructional Method (TIM). It was also revealed that the male students have higher mean performance scores than female students taught with MMIS. This implies that mind mapping instructional strategy significantly improved students' performance in technical education programs. It is recommended that technical education teachers should encourage their students to imbibe the use of mind mapping instructional strategy during teaching and learning process among others.

Keywords: Effect, mind mapping, gender, performance.

Introduction

In today's evolving educational landscape, technical education particularly in colleges of education plays a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge, skills, initiative and sense of responsibility necessary to the world's sustainable development as educators strive to refine teaching methods and improve learning outcomes, the integration of new ideas such as thought boards is gaining attraction. The National Commission of Colleges of Education (NCCE) (2021) defines technical education as a field focused on the study of technology, its characteristics, methods, processes and uses. Education includes the knowledge and skills required to understand, use and manage technology effectively in a variety of settings, including business and society. It is also an integrated programme that interacts with other programmes related to human development at the professional level in business, industry and even agriculture.

The mind-mapping instructional strategy is a recent development in technical education, designed to help students acquire skills and knowledge through a structured and organized process. This approach enhances learning outcomes in

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technical education classrooms by teaching students to create visual representations of mental maps that depict complex ideas in layers and interactions. By incorporating concepts, colors, and images to form words, students can better understand and retain material. The strategy aims to foster deeper understanding, critical thinking, and engagement with the content. Through the mind-mapping process, students can collect and organize information, identify relationships between concepts, and gain a clearer understanding of the subject matter." This shows that technical education can help countries acquire scientific knowledge and the skills necessary for their survival and growth, as supported by semantic studies, mind maps, and other methods (Eppler, 2006; Parikh, 2015). Buzan and Buzan (2010) stated that thinking in context means using diagrams to visualize concepts, ideas, and relationships related to subjects. It is a tool used to organize information so that students can understand complex concepts more easily, see connections between different concepts, and remember information better. Mind mapping in technical education is especially important in subjects such as metalwork, automotive, electrical-electronics, architecture, carpentry, and mathematics because these subjects involve many conceptual interactions and processes that need to be understood. This is great for getting information in and out of the brain. Using mind maps has become a creative and effective writing method that can capture ideas. This technique integrates important skills, words, pictures, mathematics, logic, rhythm, color, and spatial awareness in a unique and powerful way. Finally, the goal of using mind mapping as an instructional strategy is to improve learning outcomes by enabling students to understand and navigate the complexities of technical education.

Although the importance of science and technology education for technological development worldwide is widely acknowledged, students' performance remains below expectations (Ballah & Ugwumba, 2015). Researchers such as Ogunleye & Babajide (2011), Harry (2011), and King & Aru (2014) have identified various contributing factors, including students' poor attitude toward technical education, lack of motivation, and inadequate teaching environments. Furthermore, inadequate educational frameworks and evolving perspectives on technical education underscore the need for effective teaching strategies, which are considered crucial (Oladejo, Olosunde, Ojebisi, & Isola, 2011). It is necessary to raise graduates who can utilize modern teaching tools, analyze critical and logical situations, and contribute to advancements in science and technology. To bring the education system to a level that meets societal needs, it is essential to cultivate students who engage in long-term learning through practice and experience. This can be achieved by implementing daily learning, active learning, questioning, critical thinking, and effective teaching methods and strategies, rather than relying on outdated approaches that fail to promote genuine understanding.

Traditional teaching is a teacher-centered approach where teachers are viewed as the primary authorities in imparting knowledge to students. However, it is well-documented that students in conventional classrooms often experience a lack of interest and participation in the learning process. Despite its drawbacks, traditional teaching methods are still favored by some technical educators because they allow for the coverage of extensive topics and reach large groups of students within a short time frame. Unlike modern visualization-based teaching tools, traditional methods do not encourage students to take responsibility for their own learning. In contrast, innovative teaching methods, such as mind-mapping strategies, address students' learning, knowledge, and skill needs. These methods enable teachers to identify students' weaknesses and address them effectively, fostering a learning process tailored to their cognitive development.

Mind mapping according to Bada & Folashade (2020) is a visualization tool used in instruction that can be applied by learners to generate ideas, take note, organize thinking and develop concepts. Instruction using mind mapping is becoming increasingly commonly used in education. However, research has produced consistent results regarding the effectiveness of mind mapping based instruction on student learning outcomes in all subjects especially in the science, technology, engineering and mathematics among others. The students with poor academic performance are more susceptible to the impact of mind mapping based instruction than students with high performance in technical education concepts in the midst of these challenges, the teacher is expected to perform efficiently. The Individual differences among students have led to the teacher to explore this instructional method to meet the diverse needs. Therefore, mind mapping has been found to have a more positive impact of students' cognitive learning outcome than traditional instructional method. This shows that content and learning level are important factors in the effectiveness of mind mapping as a teaching method.

Academic Performance is the outcome of instruction and success is the result of teaching. According to Konyefa and Okigbo (2021), this is the score obtained from the performance test that teachers take to measure whether teaching objectives have been achieved. Academic success is often a reflection of what students have accomplished through a course or courses. Student performance refers to performance in school subjects as determined by grades or scores obtained from performance tests (Abd, Andi, and Muhammad, 2020). Performance is measured by performance standards developed for school programmes. In this study, performance is evaluated as the student's score on the standardized test according to the instructional

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content. Nwankwo (2018) argued that grades are mostly time-based and depend on how well students can retain the material. This is because, unlike students who insist on meaningful learning, students who engage in rote learning have poor understanding and have difficulty in using the procedural knowledge acquired while solving problems determined in the learning process. According to Borich (2011), it is important to ensure effective learning if teachers adapt teaching to meet the different learning needs of male and female students, regardless of their gender. The impact of gender and its interaction with teaching strategies remains unclear. Research shows that some teaching methods benefit males more than females, while others report the opposite. Some teaching methods may be gender-specific (Izuegbunam, 2018; Konyefa and Okigbo, 2021), while others may be more gender specific or specific (Nwanze and Okoli, 2021).

The literature revealed that there has been an increasing interest in innovative teaching strategies, particularly cognitive strategies, aimed at enhancing the learning skills of technical education students, raising educational standards, and promoting global development. While the benefits of brain maps as cognitive tools for learning are widely acknowledged, gaps remain in understanding their specific impact on technical education students' learning abilities in the context of colleges of education. Therefore, the main question of this study is to investigate the influence of mind mapping on technical education concepts among technical education students in colleges of education focusing on its ability to contribute to the sustainable global development. This requires investigating the impact of mind mapping instructional strategy in promoting understanding as well as improving the academic performance in the use of ideas and skills to stimulate student critical thinking, problem solving and creativity. However, effective teaching strategies should improve student performance regardless of the student's background. Since the effect of educational change on students is not yet known, the effect of mental teaching strategies depending on the gender of the job will need to be examined. However, it is known that students' participation in the learning process can increase permanence (Neboh, 2009). Because students' participation in the learning process reveals personal learning experiences and a variety of practical tools that can help change and improve the process. Additionally, this study aims to promote a culture of continuous improvement in colleges of education by highlighting the importance of new teaching strategies that focus on the understanding of technical education students with special needs. By using the power of mind mapping and other methods, teachers can encourage their students to partner in creating a successful and prosperous future around the world.

Objective of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the effect of mind mapping instructional strategy on performance in technical education among colleges of education students in South-West, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out;

1. Difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.
2. Difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions raised to guide the study;

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria?
2. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS) in colleges of education in South-West?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

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The study adopted the pre-test, post-test control group non-equivalent quasi experimental design. This study involved two colleges of education in Lagos and Ogun States, South-West, Nigeria. According to Nworgu (2015), a study is considered a quasi-experimental design when random assignment of subjects to experimental and control groups is not possible and as such intact or pre-existing groups are used. The choice of quasi-experiment design therefore was because the administrative set up in the colleges does not allow for randomization of students for experiment as it may disrupt academic activities. The sample of the study involved 109 technical education students from two colleges of education located in Lagos and Ogun states, South-West, Nigeria. The sampling involved both purposive and random techniques. The colleges were chosen because they are of similar characteristics in terms of the regulatory body the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE); student types, and presence of skilled and experienced teachers as well as teaching and learning resources. The purposive and random sampling techniques were used, with the colleges sampled including Federal College of Education (T) Akoka, Lagos State and Oba Sikiru Adetona College of Science and Technology Education in Omu Ijebu, Ogun State. The NCE II Class of Oba Sikiru Adetona College of Science and Technology Education was used as the control group while Federal College of Education (T), Akoka, Lagos State served as the experimental group. The control college had a total of 50 students, (29 male and 21 female) while the experimental college had a total of 59 students (32 males & 27 females). The Technical Education Performance Test (TEPT) instrument in technical education concepts. TEPT was developed by the researcher for data collection. It was made up of sections A and B. Section A was concerned with the personal data of students while Section B contains the test items. The TEPT was used for collection of pretest and posttest performance scores. The TEPT items were made up of 20 multiple choice questions with four options. The items in the test, covered all the units of technical education concepts that were taught. It was used to administer pretest and posttest for both experimental and control groups. After administration of Pretest, the question papers were collected so as to prevent the students from using it as a revision guide before the posttest. Two lesson notes were prepared by the researcher for teaching technical education concepts. One of the lesson notes was written based on traditional instructional method and it was used for teaching technical education concepts to the control group, while the other was written based on the Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS), and was used to teach technical education concepts to the experimental group. The instrument used for data collection was validated by three experts from department of Science and Technology education, University of Lagos. The instrument was validated in terms of simplicity of instruction, wordings of items, adequacy and level of coverage of items in addressing the purpose of the study. Corrections and comments given by the experts were used in restructuring the items. The corrected items were then administered to the students. Reliability of the instrument was established through pilot test which was conducted in a college of education different from the sampled colleges used for the research. Test-retest method was used to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Test was initially given as pretest and then administered a week later as post-test, the results from pretest and post-test were compared to ascertain the reliability of the instrument. Scores from both tests were then correlated using the Cronbach Alpha in estimating the reliability coefficient. Internal consistency of 0.76 was obtained. The result obtained indicated that the item is reliable for the research and can serve the purpose for which it was developed. The TEPT was administered by the researcher and trained research assistants as pre-test to both experimental and control group. Objective question papers containing 20 items were given to students to tick the correct answer. The papers were retrieved from the students after the pre-test and marked by the researcher to obtain students' scores on academic performance before treatment was administered. This gave a clear picture of students' performance before the treatment. The control college had a total of 50 students (29 male and 21 female), while the experimental college had a total of 59 students (32 male and 27 female). The Technical Education Performance Test (TEPT), developed by the researcher, was used to collect data on technical education concepts. It consisted of Sections A and B. Section A focused on the personal data of students, while Section B contained the test items. The TEPT was used to collect pretest and post-test performance scores. The test included 20 multiple-choice questions with four options, covering all the units of technical education concepts that were taught. It was administered as both a pretest and post-test to both the experimental and control groups. After the pretest was administered, the question papers were collected to prevent students from using them as a revision guide before the post-test.

The researcher prepared two lesson plans for teaching technical education concepts: one based on the traditional instructional method for the control group, and the other based on the Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS) for the experimental group. The data collection instrument was validated by three experts from the Department of Science and Technology Education at the University of Lagos. The validation assessed the simplicity of the instructions, the wording of the items, and the adequacy and coverage of the items in relation to the study's purpose. Corrections and comments from the experts were used to restructure the items, which were then administered to the students. The reliability of the instrument was established through a pilot test conducted at a different college of education. The test-retest method was used to verify

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reliability: the pretest was administered, followed by the same test one week later as a post-test. The results of the pretest and post-test were compared to establish reliability. The scores from both tests were correlated using Cronbach's Alpha to estimate the reliability coefficient, which was found to be 0.76, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the research. The TEPT was administered by the researcher and trained research assistants as a pretest to both the experimental and control groups. The objective test papers containing 20 items were distributed to the students, who were asked to mark the correct answers. After the pretest, the papers were collected and graded by the researcher to determine the students' academic performance before the treatment was applied. This provided a clear picture of the students' performance prior to the intervention.

The researcher prepared lesson notes for the traditional instructional method used in teaching the control group and also lesson notes based on the mind mapping instructional strategy used in teaching the experimental group. The researcher guided and explained to the trained research assistants on how to go about teaching the experimental group. After one week, the researcher and the trained research assistants administered a post-test to measure performance. The post-test items were the same items used in administering the pretest. The papers for the TEPT were retrieved back from the students after the post-test and marked by the researcher to obtain the students' performance scores after treatment. Data generated from the TEPT technical education concepts were subjected to statistical analysis to find the descriptive statistics and t-test was used to find out if there is significant difference in the academic performance mean score of the experimental and control groups and also that of retention mean scores of the experimental and control students taught using MMIS.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Performance Scores of Students taught Technical Education concepts using Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS) and those taught using Traditional Instructional Method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria

Group	X	Pre-test (X)	Pre-test (SD)	Post-test (X)	Post-test (SD)	Mean Gained
MMIS	59	25.41	9.73	73.75	8.27	48.34
TIM	50	21.99	9.34	68.70	6.53	46.71
Mean difference		.41		5.05		1.63

Table 1 reveals that the students taught technical education concepts using MMIS has pretest mean performance score of 25.41 and posttest mean performance score of 73.75 with mean gained performance score of 48.34, while those in the control group taught with traditional instructional method has pretest mean performance score of 21.99 and posttest mean score of 68.70 with mean gained 46.71. Students taught technical education concepts using MMIS had a less homogeneous score in their posttest (5.05) than those taught using TIM (3.41). The difference between the between the mean gained performance scores of the students is 1.63 in favour of MMIS.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS) in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria.?

Table 2: mean performance scores of male and female students taught technical education concepts using MMIS in colleges of education in South-West Nigeria.

Gender	X	Pre-test (X)	Pre-test (SD)	Post-test (X)	Post-test (SD)	Mean Gained
Male	32	25.44	9.63	79.41	5.44	53.97

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional ... (Dawodu, et. al., 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073605>

Female	27	23.78	10.02	68.04	6.02	44.26
Mean difference		1.66		11.37		9.71

Table 2 reveals that the male students taught technical education concepts using MMIS has pretest mean performance score of 25.44 and post-test mean performance score of 79.40 with mean gained performance score of 53.97, while those the female students had pretest mean performance score of 23.78 and post-test mean performance score of 68.04 with gained mean 44.26. Male students taught concepts of technology using MMIS had a more homogeneous score in their post-test 11.37 than the female 1.66. The difference between the mean gained performance scores of the male and female students is 9.71 in favour of males.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional strategy (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Table 3: ANCOVA Test of Significance of Difference between the Mean Performance Scores of Students taught technical education concepts using MMIS and TIM in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	f	Sig	Decision
Corrected mode	2842.978	4	710.745	19.215	.000	
Intercept	72279.511	1	72279.511	1954.053	.000	
Pretest	47.627	1	47.627	1.288	.259	
Method	300.331	1	300.331	8.119	.005	sig
Gender	1631.363	1	1631.363	44.103	.000	sig
Method Gender	554.780	1	554.780	14.998	.000	sig
Error	3846.912	104	36.990			
Total	570163.000	109				
Corrected Total	6689.890	108				

Table 3 shows that there is a significant main effect of the treatment on students' performance scores in technical education concepts $F(4, 104) = 8.119, P = 0.005 < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using mind mapping instructional approach (MMIS) and those taught using traditional instructional method (TIM) in favour of MMIS.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in technical education concepts in colleges of education in South-West, Nigeria.

Table 4 t-test analysis of the post-test mean scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	tcal	p-value	Remarks
Male	32	25.44	2.582	49	0.866	0.567	Significant
Female	27	23.78	2.887				

Not significant at $P > 0.05$

The result presents the t-test analysis for mean post-test scores of male and female students taught using MMIS. The test was conducted to determine if the mean difference of 25.44 for male and 23.78 for female was significant or not. The t-cal of 0.866 was however found not to be significant at 0.05 level ($t=0.577, df=49, P=0.567$). Therefore, the null hypothesis that the performance scores of students taught the technical education concepts using MMIS is not significantly affected by gender is accepted. Table 4 shows that there is a significant impact of gender in students' retention of technical education concepts F

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(4, 104) = 44.103, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected meaning that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in technical education concepts in favour of the males

Discussion of Findings

This study showed a significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught technical education concepts using the Mind Mapping Instructional Strategy (MMIS) and those taught using the Traditional Instructional Method (TIM), with the results favoring MMIS. This outcome was attributed to the fact that students exposed to the MMIS had their academic needs met, as they received remedial instruction on the technical education concepts necessary to enhance their understanding of the material being taught. In this way, teachers differentiate teaching and learning in ways that make learning more effective for students. By exposing students to the mind mapping strategy to ensure they grasp technical education concepts and master the learning materials, students are engaged in a rich and meaningful learning experience. The use of the mind mapping strategy also allows students to learn at their own pace and interact with the teacher regarding the learning materials. Through mind mapping students have ample time to understand the content by connecting it with related concepts, making learning a motivating transformative experience. Again, the use of mind mapping strategy helps the students to learn at their own pace and allowing students to interact with the teacher on the learning materials. Using mind mapping, students have sufficient time to understand the content by exploring related concepts, which fosters motivation and drives positive change in their learning experience. The study contradicts Bada and Folashade (2020) who compared the curriculum to traditional guidelines and showed that student learning, as measured by two tests which differ across scores based on key instructional differences. The results of the study support the finding of Adodo (2013) that students who are taught to self-regulated learning strategy are more effective in improving their academic performance than students who do not use this method. The results of the study are in line with the finding of Izuegbunam and Osuafor (2021) that students who use the adaptive learning approach always achieve better results compared to classroom teaching by expert and other educational changes. The finding of the study showed that there is a significant difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students in chemistry. A significant interaction was found between teaching method and gender on students' chemistry performance. Adaptive learning favoured the males more than the females in their achievement. The results of this study are not consistent with the findings of Nwankwo (2018) and Lttenberger Pachter and Ertl (2019) who found no significant difference in the performance of males and females when using individualized instructional method. However, the results of the study support the finding of Ikwumelu, Oyinbe and Oketa (2015), and it was revealed that boys in experimental group, scored higher than girls in the Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) pre-test, but there was a significant difference in the mean scores after treatment. This implies that the boys have higher mean performance scores than the girls.

Conclusion

The results of this study showed that students taught technology using Mind mapping instructional strategy had significantly higher performance scores than those taught using traditional instructional method. It is concluded that MMIS is an effective instructional strategy in improving students' academic performance in technical education concepts. The study also found that, gender had significant impact on students' performance in technical education concepts. The findings of the study concluded that the mind mapping instructional strategy affect males and female students differently.

Recommendations

Based on the findings above, the followings were made;

1. Mind mapping instructional approach significantly improved students' performance in technical education programmes hence it is recommended to the teaching in NCCE technical education programmes.
2. Technical education lecturers should encourage their students to imbibe the use of mind mapping instructional approach during teaching learning process
3. Technical education curriculum experts be encouraged to integrate mind mapping instructional approach into the NCCE technical education curriculum so that students of colleges of education can be expose to the use of this instructional approach.
4. Conferences, Seminars and Workshops be organized for lecturers of colleges of education on how to use mind mapping instructional approach to improve their teaching.

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References

- Akanbi, A.O, Olayinka. W, Omosewo, E.O & Mohammed, R.E. (2021). Effect of mind mapping Instructional strategy on students' retention in Physics in senior Secondary Schools. *Anatolian. Journal of Education*. 6(1), 145-156
- Adodo, S. O. (2013). Effect of mind-mapping as a self-regulated learning strategy on students' Achievement in basic science and technology. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Science*, 4 (6), 163172.
<https://doi.org/10.5901/mjss.2013.v4n6p163>
- Abd, B., Andi, S. and Muhammad, A.I. (2020). Academic self-efficacy as predictor of academic achievement. *Journal Pendidikan Indonesia*, 9(1), 163-168.
- Al-Zyoud, A. A., Al Jamal, D., & Bani abdelrahman, A. (2017). Mind mapping and students' writing performance. *Arab World English Journal*, 8(4), 28291. <https://doi.org/10.24093/awej/vol8no4.19>
- Buzan, T. & Buzan, B. (2010). *The mind map book: unlock your creativity, boost your memory, change your life*. Arlow, UK: Pearson.
- Borich, G. D. (2011) *Effective teaching methods*. UK: Institute of Technology Press.
- Bada, A.A & Folashade, A, (2020). Effect of Mind Mapping Teaching Method on Senior Secondary School Students Achievement in Physics in Ondo State, Nigeria. *Journal of Curriculum and Instruction*. 3(1), 86-96
- Bada, A.A & Akinbobola, A. O. (2017). Effectiveness of Experiential Teaching Strategy on Students Achievement and Scoring levels in Senior Secondary School Physics. *European Journal of Education Studies*, 3(12), 552-564.
- Ballah, A.G & Ugwumba, A.O.(2015). Attitude and Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics in Nigeria. Paper Presented at the proceedings of SOCOINTER15-2nd International Conference in Education, Social Sciences and Humanities (pp499-508), Istanbul, Turkey.
- Eppler, M.J.(2006). A comparison between concept maps, mind maps, conceptual diagrammes, and visual metaphors as complementary tools for knowledge construction and sharing. *Information visualization*. 5 (3), 202-210.
- Harry, I.H. (2011). Attitude of Students towards Science and Science Education in Nigeria. (A case study of Selected Secondary Schools in Rivers State). *Continental J. of Educational Research*, 4 (2), 33-51
- Izuegbunam, A. G. & Osuafor, A. M (2021). (Effect of Adaptive Learning Approach on Students' Achievement in Chemistry in Awka Education Zone of Anambra State. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation* 7 (5), 81-89
- Izuegbunam, A. G. & Osuafor, A. M, (2021). Effect of Adaptive Learning Approach on Students' Retention In Chemistry In Awka Education Zone Of Anambra State. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*. 11 (6), 22 28
- Izuegbunam, A. G. (2018). Effect of cooperative and individualized instruction on students' achievement in chemistry in Awka south local government area. Unpublished Master's thesis submitted to Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- King'aru, J.M.(2014). Factors Contributing to Poor Performance of Science Subjects: A case study Secondary Schools in Kawe Division Municipality. M,Ed Dissertation, Open University of Tanzania
- Konyefa, B.I. and Okigbo, E.C. (2021). Effect of ethnochemistry instructional approach on secondary school students' achievement in chemistry in Bayelsa State. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation (IJEE)*, 7(4), 16-22.
- Ikwumelu, S. N., Oyibe O. A. and Oketa, E. C (2015) Adaptive teaching: An invaluable Pedagogic practice in Social Studies Education. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 6(33), 140 – 144.
- Katcha, M. A, Orji, A.B.C, Ebele, F. U, Abubakar, Z. & Mohammed, B. (2018). Effects of Mind Mapping instructional Approach on Senior Secondary School Biology Students' Achievement in Evolution in Minna, Niger State, Nigeria. *Journal of Science, Technology, Mathematics and Education (JOSTMED)*, 14(2), 146-154
- Luttenberger, S., Paechter, M. and Ertl, B. (2019). Self-concept and support experienced in school as key variables for the motivation of women enrolled in STEM subjects with a low and moderate proportion of females. *Frontier Psychology*, 10, 12-42. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01242

Effect of Mind Mapping Instructional ... (Dawodu, et. al., 2024): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15073605>

- NCCE (2021). Nigeria Certificate in Education Minimum Standard for general education. Abuja: National Commission for colleges of Education.
- Neboh, O. I. (2009). Effect of learning activity package (LAP) on students' achievement and retention in senior secondary school biology. Unpublished Thesis, Department of Science Education Faculty of Education University of Nigeria, Nsukka
- Nworgu B.G (2015). Educational Research: Basic Issues and Methods. Nsukka, University Trust Publishers. Nwankwo, G.U. (2018). Effect of activity based instructional on junior secondary school students' achievement and retention in basic science. Unpublished theses, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.
- Nwanze, A. C. and Okoli, J.N. (2021). Path analysis of factors affecting academic achievement of tertiary education students in chemistry in Delta state. *African Journal of Science, Technology & Mathematics Education*, 6(1), 75-88.
- Nwanze, A.C., Konyefa, B.I. and Ezeanya, C.M. (2021). Cognitive style as a determinant of academic achievement of secondary school science students in Onitsha Education Zone. *International Journal of Education and Evaluation*, 7(2), 12-24.
- Oladejo, M.A., Olosunde, G.R., Ojebisi, A.O., & Isola, O.M. (2011). Instructional materials and students 'academic achievement in physics. Some Policy Implications. *European Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(1), 112-126.
- Parikh, N.D. (2015). Mind map and concept map as complementary tools for teaching. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*. 2(4, 147-158S)